

**Strategic Work Plan for the Institute of Science and Technology
(IoST), Tribhuvan University**

Prepared for the post of Dean
Institute of Science and Technology
Tribhuvan University

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1. Background and Context

The Institute of Science and Technology (IoST) is an esteemed academic institution under Tribhuvan University, contributing significantly to the advancement of higher education in Nepal, with a particular focus on science and technology. IoST has made substantial contributions to the scientific, technological, and educational development of the country since its establishment. IoST is one of the largest institutes within Tribhuvan University, serving approximately 38,000 students. The institution has a different academic levels, with approximately 33,000 undergraduate students, 4,000 master's students, 413 PhD and 10 postdoctoral scholars. These students are spread across 13 Central Departments, 1 school, 24 constituent campuses, and 89 affiliated campuses.

The IoST offers a wide range of research-driven Master's and PhD programs, attracting a growing number of scholars who are actively involved in advanced research in fields such as pure science, environmental science, biotechnology, data science, and information technology. IoST also places a strong emphasis on promoting collaborative exchange programs with academic institutions both nationally and internationally. These programs aim to enhance the competency of faculty, research scholars, and students. The collaborative approach of IoST is in line with their vision of becoming a center of excellence in science and technology education. It offers advanced laboratories, libraries, and consulting services to support this vision.

The recent socio-political changes in Nepal, such as the federalization of the country, bring about a range of opportunities and challenges for IoST. The institution must now adjust to a rapidly changing educational scenery, as there are higher expectations for higher education institutions to produce competent graduates who can effectively contribute to national development. The strategic work plan of IoST focuses on enhancing its capacity in research, teaching, and collaboration, in line with Tribhuvan University's Vision 2030 to achieve global recognition for academic excellence.

2. Vision and Objectives

IoST aims to establish itself as a renowned institution for science and technology education and research in Nepal. The institution aims to enhance academic excellence by promoting impactful teaching, innovative studies, and partnerships with both local and global institutions. The key objectives of IoST are:

- To provide adequate infrastructure for research and teaching.
- To introduce new and relevant subjects in science and technology.
- To produce high-skilled manpower with strong knowledge bases.
- To mobilize resources for research and development.
- To organize national and international seminars, conferences, and workshops.
- To conduct refresher courses to enhance faculty proficiency.

3. Strategic Direction and Core Strategies

To achieve these objectives, the following major strategies are outlined: each is vital for driving progress, encouraging innovation, and assuring long-term growth within the institution. These strategies will serve as the framework for future initiatives, ensuring that they are consistent with the overarching vision and address both current and long-term objectives.

3.1 Strengthening Research Infrastructure

IoST will allocate sufficient budget to upgrading laboratories and establishing new research centers focusing on new advances in science or technology. This will support faculty and students in conducting high-impact research, with funding secured through national and international grants.

3.2 Curriculum Development and Innovation

The curriculum will be regularly updated in collaboration with industry experts to ensure it remains in line with market needs. Interdisciplinary programs such as Data Science, Material Science, Biotechnology, Environmental Technology and Artificial Intelligence will be focused, preparing students for both national development and the global job market. IoST will also strengthen problem-based learning to encourage creativity and critical thinking.

3.3 Digital Transformation

A comprehensive Learning Management System (LMS) will be implemented effectively, providing students and faculty with access to online courses, digital libraries, and research tools. The digitization effort will cover administrative processes, from student admissions to online entrance examination systems. This will make IoST a leader in digital education in Nepal.

3.4 Quality Assurance Accreditation

IoST will set up a periodic review mechanism for academic programs and faculty performance to ensure continuous improvement. The institute will work towards QAA certification for all its departments, schools and campuses, strengthening its global reputation and making its degrees internationally recognized.

3.5 International Collaboration and Partnerships

IoST will prioritize the establishment of strong alliances with international universities, research institutions, and industries. These collaborations will promote joint research projects, student exchanges, and dual-degree programs, which will greatly expand the international presence of IoST. In addition, MoUs with private companies will help provide internships and job placements for students, strengthening the connection between academia and industry.

3.6 Financial Sustainability

IoST will diversify its revenue streams by introducing short-term certification courses in high-demand areas. The institute will establish a consultancy wing offering expert services in fields such as IT, AI, Biotechnology and Environmental science to generate additional income. An IoST endowment fund will be created to support student scholarships and infrastructure development, ensuring financial sustainability.

4. Strategic Actions

The specific objectives and actionable steps required to successfully implement these core strategies are as follows. Each objective is carefully designed to address key challenges, optimize resources, and unlock new opportunities, ensuring measurable progress toward our overall mission. These actions will serve as the driving force behind the transformation, providing a clear roadmap to achieve both short-term wins and long-term institutional success.

4.1. Infrastructure Development for Research and Education

- **Objective:** To establish IoST as a research hub by upgrading its infrastructure to meet international standards.

Actions:

- Upgrade laboratories across all Central Departments with modern research equipment to support advanced scientific inquiry.
- Establish a central digital library with access to international research journals and databases to enhance academic and research activities.
- Develop dedicated research centers focusing on emerging fields such as Renewable Energy, Biotechnology, Data Science, Material Science and Artificial Intelligence.
- Improve infrastructure at constituent campuses, ensuring they are equipped with smart classrooms and digital tools for blended learning.
- Expand campus facilities to accommodate increased student enrollment and support large-scale research projects.

4.2. Curriculum Innovation and Expansion

- **Objective:** To ensure IoST's curriculum remains relevant and aligned with global scientific advancements and market demands.
- **Actions:**
 - Periodically update the curriculum in consultation with industry partners, ensuring alignment with market needs and technological advancements.
 - Introduce interdisciplinary programs in emerging areas.
 - Strengthen partnerships with industries to include internships, projects, and practical experiences as part of the academic programs.
 - Promote problem-based learning methodologies to enhance critical thinking and problem-solving skills among students.
 - Empower faculty board to ensure the curriculum stays aligned with national development goals and international standards.

4.3. Faculty Development and Academic Excellence

- **Objective:** To cultivate a culture of continuous professional development for IoST faculty to enhance their academic and research capabilities.
- **Actions:**
 - Implement faculty development programs focusing on research methodologies, pedagogy, and digital teaching tools.
 - Organize international exchange programs for faculty to gain exposure to global trends in science and technology education.

- Encourage faculty participation in national and international conferences and provide financial support for research publication.
- Introduce mentorship programs within IoST where senior faculty provide guidance on research projects and teaching innovations.
- Establish performance evaluation systems to reward excellence in teaching, research, and administrative roles.

4. 4. Research and Innovation Promotion

- **Objective:** To establish IoST as a leader in scientific research and innovation in Nepal.
- **Actions:**
 - Develop a dedicated research fund to support high-impact research projects and provide seed funding for emerging researchers.
 - Strengthen collaboration with ministries, industries, and research institutions to enhance applied research and innovation.
 - Organize annual research symposiums and innovation fairs, inviting participation from scientists, industries, and students.
 - Establish specialized research clusters focusing on priority areas.
 - Provide incentives for faculty and students to publish research papers in high-impact journals and present their findings at global forums.

4. 5. Digitization and Technology Integration

- **Objective:** To modernize IoST's academic and administrative processes through the integration of digital technologies.
- **Actions:**
 - Implement a comprehensive Learning Management System (LMS) for all academic programs, providing students and faculty with online learning tools.
 - Introduce digital platforms for student enrollment, examination management, and administrative processes to streamline operations.
 - Upgrade IT infrastructure across campuses to ensure high-speed internet connectivity, especially in research and innovation centers.
 - Promote the use of big data and AI tools in academic research to drive innovation and address national challenges.
 - Establish online portals for research collaboration and knowledge sharing between faculty, students, and industry partners.

4. 6. Collaboration and Partnerships

- **Objective:** To enhance academic and research collaboration with national and international partners.
- **Actions:**
 - Establish MoUs with international universities and research institutes to facilitate exchange programs and collaborative research.
 - Strengthen partnerships with government ministries, such as the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Science and Technology, and private industries to promote applied research.

- Leverage existing international collaborations with organizations like the World Bank and UGC Nepal to secure research grants.
- Organize joint seminars, conferences, and workshops with partner institutions to share knowledge and research findings.
- Collaborate with the private sector to create internship opportunities for students and industry-relevant research projects.

4. 7. Financial Sustainability and Resource Mobilization

- **Objective:** To ensure the long-term financial sustainability of IoST through diversified funding sources.
- **Actions:**
 - Explore opportunities for public-private partnerships to support infrastructure development and research initiatives.
 - Establish IoST as a consultancy hub, offering expertise to industries and government bodies in areas like IT.
 - Develop short-term certification courses in emerging fields like Data Science, Artificial Intelligence, and Renewable Energy to generate revenue.
 - Create an IoST endowment fund aimed at supporting student scholarships, research grants, and infrastructure development.
 - Utilize grants from national bodies (e.g., UGC Nepal) and international agencies to finance large-scale research projects and innovation initiatives.

4. 8. Student-Centered Learning and Support

- **Objective:** To promote a student-centered learning environment that promotes academic success and personal growth.
- **Actions:**
 - Establish student counseling services to offer academic guidance, career counseling, and mental health support.
 - Create student-led clubs focused on innovation, technology, and research, fostering a community of engaged learners.
 - Provide scholarships and financial aid to ensure access to education for students from disadvantaged backgrounds.
 - Organize innovation fairs and hackathons, offering students opportunities to showcase their research and projects.
 - Develop a peer mentoring program where senior students guide and support incoming students in academic and research activities.

4. 9. Quality Assurance and Accreditation

- **Objective:** To ensure continuous quality improvement and global recognition through the Quality Assurance and Accreditation (QAA) process.
- **Actions:**
 - Empower all departments, schools, and campuses to work towards QAA certification by organizing training programs, workshops, and seminars in coordination with UGC Nepal.

- Provide necessary resources and guidance for departments to meet QAA standards.
- Set up an internal monitoring committee to oversee progress on QAA-related activities.
- Collaborate with UGC Nepal to ensure departments are well-prepared for the accreditation process.
- Introduce annual reviews to track the status of departments, schools, and campuses regarding their QAA progress.

5. Monitoring and Implementation Plan

The monitoring and evaluation process will follow a structured framework to ensure the timely achievement of the outlined objectives. A Strategic Implementation Committee (SIC) will be formed, comprising senior faculty, administrative staff, and student representatives. The committee will oversee the allocation of resources, monitor progress, and address challenges that arise during implementation.

Key Monitoring Tools:

1. **Bi-annual Departmental Reports:** Each Department will submit progress reports detailing achievements, challenges, and next steps related to their specific objectives.
2. **Quarterly Reviews:** The SIC will hold quarterly meetings to review the progress of strategic actions and make adjustments if necessary.
3. **Performance Metrics:** Evaluation will be based on a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):
 - Number of research publications by faculty and students.
 - New courses introduced and accredited.
 - Percentage of faculty involved in international exchanges.
 - Funds generated through research grants and partnerships.
 - Student satisfaction surveys conducted annually to assess academic and administrative improvements.

Evaluation Process:

The evaluation process will include both quantitative and qualitative assessments, with a focus on the timely completion of strategic goals. Each department will be responsible for collecting data on its initiatives, while the SIC will compile and analyze the data to inform decision-making process. Annual reviews will determine whether targets have been met, and necessary adjustments will be made to the action plans.

6. Conclusion

This strategic work plan provides a holistic framework for transforming the Institute of Science and Technology (IoST) into a premier national hub for science and technology education, fully aligned with Tribhuvan University's Vision 2030. By focusing on research excellence, improving infrastructure, building international partnerships, and adopting digital solutions, IoST will be ready to face the changing challenges in higher education in Nepal.

With clear objectives, targeted initiatives, and rigorous monitoring in place, IoST will not only achieve its institutional goals but also play a pivotal role in advancing national progress. The focus on producing highly skilled graduates and conducting groundbreaking research will have far-reaching impacts on Nepal's scientific, technological, and socioeconomic development.

The strategic actions outlined are designed to ensure IoST remains a forward-thinking, innovative institution, continuously adapting to global trends and leading advancements in science and technology. Through this plan, IoST is committed to shaping the future of education and research in Nepal, ensuring its relevance and leadership for decades to come.

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